

Assessment of the Efficacy of Turbulence Models in the Simulation of Violent Sloshing

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ABSTRACT

Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes simulations (RANS) have been widely utilised to provide representation of sloshing dynamics with a balance between the reliability and cost. However, a clear answer as to the effectiveness of standard RANS closure models for the simulation of sloshing problems is yet to be found [1]. In our recent work [1], simulations of partially filled closed-tank subjected to harmonically oscillating and vertical motion were presented. A Volume of Fluid modelling approach was used to capture the air–water interface. Simulations with no model and with different RANS closure models were conducted to demonstrate the efficacy of using a standard RANS approach in the simulation of weak and violent sloshing flows. It was found that standard RANS models can overestimate the turbulent viscosity at the interface, which lead to excessive damping of the liquid motions, leading to underestimation of the total sloshing damping effect, as seen in figure 1. Simulations without a turbulence model do not have this issue and, as a result, better results are often produced where turbulent effects do not dominate. Larsen and Fuhrman [2] proposed a modified RANS models where the turbulent viscosity are modulated at the interface, which have the potential of improving the stability and the accuracy. In this work, the efficacy of the modified models for the simulation of wide range of well-defined and industrially-derived sloshing conditions will be investigated and compared with the standard models.

Figure 1: The left figure is the computed dissipated as a function of Fr numbers and compared with experimental data [3]. Right figure is the hysteresis of the averaged damping force with the displacement for $Fr = 1.85$.

REFERENCES

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